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Hydraulic Conditions During Liquid Flow Through Sorbent Materials

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Abstract. This contribution presents an experimental analysis of the static characteristics of selected sorbent materials under liquid flow conditions. The study focuses on cenospheres—lightweight microspherical particles formed as a by-product of coal combustion—tested in several distinct particle size fractions, as well as on a ceramic granulate of defined fraction. A dedicated experimental setup was constructed, featuring a modular filtration unit designed to ensure the stable placement of the sorbent material. The sorbent was secured within the filtration chamber using geotextile membranes. During the tests, flow rates and the corresponding pressure drops were systematically measured for each material fraction. Based on the collected data, characteristic curves showing pressure drop as a function of flow rate were plotted. The results enable a comparison of the hydraulic resistance of the individual sorbents depending on their size fractions. The measured data will further support the selection of optimal sorbent materials for filtration applications, with an emphasis on minimizing pressure losses and maximizing sorption capacity—aiming at the efficient design of energy-saving filtration systems.

1. Introduction

The sorption of metal ions from aqueous solutions is a key technology in the treatment of industrial wastewater and is increasingly applied in the recovery of metals from secondary raw materials. Acidic solutions containing heavy and rare metals are predominantly generated during hydrometallurgical leaching of secondary materials such as battery waste, spent catalysts, or electronic scrap [1]. In the case of spent lithium-ion batteries, leaching of active electrode materials is typically performed using acids (e.g., H₂SO₄ or HCl), often in the presence of oxidizing agents (e.g., H₂O₂), leading to the release of metal cations—such as lithium, cobalt, nickel, manganese, and copper—into the liquid phase. These leachates contain a complex mixture of metal ions at high concentrations, and their selective separation is a critical step in the recycling process.

The efficiency of the sorption process depends not only on the chemical selectivity of the sorbent but also on its physical and hydraulic properties, particularly when applied in continuous-flow filtration columns. Key parameters include the particle size and shape, surface morphology, bulk density, porosity, and pore size distribution, all of which influence the bed permeability and available surface area for sorption [2]. The hydraulic behaviour of the packed bed—typically expressed in terms of pressure drop during liquid flow—determines

the resistance imposed on the fluid and thus the overall energy demand of the system. Very fine sorbent fractions may cause excessive pressure losses, clogging, and flow channelling, whereas coarser fractions may reduce sorption efficiency due to a smaller contact surface area.

This study aims to experimentally evaluate the static hydraulic characteristics of selected sorbent materials, namely cenospheres—lightweight microspherical particles with high porosity formed as a by-product of coal combustion—and technical cordierite-based ceramics. The materials were tested in various particle size fractions under defined flow conditions. Based on the obtained data, an optimal configuration of the filtration bed will be proposed, representing a trade-off between high sorption capacity and low pressure drop, with the goal of minimizing the energy consumption of the overall process.

2. Description of sorbent materials

When selecting an appropriate sorbent for the separation of metal ions from liquid media, it is essential to consider both the chemical properties of the material (e.g., ion affinity, stability in acidic environments) and its physical and morphological characteristics. Key morphological parameters include particle size and shape, bulk density, surface morphology, porosity, and pore size distribution. These attributes directly affect the sorbent's specific surface area and, importantly, the hydraulic behaviour of the packed sorbent bed, such as permeability and pressure drop during under flow conditions. As a result, they significantly influence the overall efficiency of the sorption process, especially when applied in flow-through column systems. This study focuses on two types of sorbent materials: cenospheres and cordierite-based technical ceramics.

2.1 Cenospheres

Cenospheres are lightweight, hollow microspherical particles formed as a by-product of coal combustion in thermal power plants [3]. Chemically, they consist mainly of aluminosilicate material, primarily silicon dioxide (SiO_2) and aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3), with variable contents of Fe_2O_3 , CaO , or MgO . Due to their low bulk density (typically $< 1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$), chemically inert behaviour, and high structural stability, cenospheres are attractive candidates for environmental applications, including the sorption of contaminants from aqueous solutions.

Morphologically, they exhibit a spherical shape, smooth external surface, and a closed hollow core. Although their walls are not microporous in the classical sense, surface modifications (e.g., etching, functionalization) can increase their specific surface area and introduce active sites suitable for metal ion adsorption. Larger particle fractions additionally offer favourable hydraulic properties and lower pressure losses in flow-through systems.

In this study, cenospheres were subjected to mechanical sieving and experimentally tested in four particle size fractions, hereafter referred to as cenosphere fractions (CF): 40–80 μm , 80–125 μm , 125–160 μm , and 160–200 μm . Each fraction was analysed in terms of pressure drop under defined flow rates to compare their hydraulic behaviour and determine their suitability for application in flow-through sorption columns.

2.2 Technical Ceramics (Cordierite)

Technical ceramics comprise a group of inorganic materials characterized by high thermal, mechanical, and chemical resistance, making them highly relevant in separation technologies. Their stability in acidic environments, dimensional integrity, and the possibility of tailored surface modification make them suitable both as sorbents and structural carriers in applications requiring mechanical robustness and chemical reactivity toward target species [4].

In this study, a cordierite-based ceramic sorbent was analysed, prepared via conventional sintering of pre-ceramic mixtures. The raw composition consisted of natural clay minerals such as kaolinite, talc, and vermiculite, combined with aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3).

The bulk densities of the different sorbent materials used for the experimental evaluation are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Bulk Densities of the Described Sorbent Materials.

Sorbent	Cordierite <40 μm	CF 40-80 μm	CF 80-125 μm	CF 125-160 μm	CF 160-200 μm
Density ρ [g·cm ⁻³]	1.08	0.445	0.431	0.428	0.425

3. Experimental setup and measurement methodology

To analyze the hydraulic properties of the selected sorbent materials, a dedicated experimental circuit was constructed to measure the pressure drop across the sorbent bed under various volumetric flow rates of liquid. The system includes a modular filtration column that ensures stable positioning of the sorbent and easy replacement between test cycles. The filtration body is designed for straightforward maintenance and efficient sorbent exchange. To ensure uniform fluid distribution across the sorbent bed, the filtration unit is equipped with an internal flow distributor. Measurements were conducted under steady-state conditions, using distilled water as the working fluid and defined particle size fractions of each sorbent material. The pressure drop between the inlet and outlet of the filtration unit was recorded continuously.

3.1 Description of the Experimental Setup

From the supply tank (T1), the liquid intended for sorption is pumped by pump (P), which is driven by an electric motor (M) with adjustable speed, allowing for regulation of the flow rate. The liquid then passes through the vertical filtration unit (F), which contains the tested sorbent material. After passing through the sorbent bed, the liquid is discharged into the receiving tank (T2). The system is equipped with a relief valve (RV) to prevent overpressure in case of excessive pressure buildup, a throttle valve (TV1) allowing flow division, and another throttle valve (TV2) used to induce backpressure. Ball valves (KV) are installed to enable fluid transfer between tanks and allow for complete drainage of both reservoirs. To monitor hydraulic performance, the apparatus includes a flowmeter (FM) and two pressure sensors (PS1 and PS2), positioned upstream and downstream of the filtration column to measure the pressure differential across the sorbent bed. Data acquisition is carried out using the MS 5070 measurement system.

The entire experimental circuit is constructed from acid-resistant materials, making it suitable not only for hydraulic characterization with water but also for real-world sorption of metal ions from acidic solutions. For the purposes of this study, only distilled water was used. A simplified schematic of the experimental setup is shown in Figure 1, and the list of system components, including their designations and partial specifications, is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Description of the Experimental Setup Components

Label	Component	Specifications
T1	Suction tank	$V = 80 \text{ dm}^3$
T2	Receiving tank	$V = 80 \text{ dm}^3$
P	Pump	$V_g = 4.3 \text{ cm}^3, p_{max} = 1000 \text{ kPa}$
EM	Electric motor	$P = 0.55 \text{ kW}, n_{max} = 1750 \text{ min}^{-1}$
RV	Relief valve	$p_{set} = 600 \text{ kPa}$
F	Filter body	
TV1, TV2	Throttle valve	
FM	Flow meter	$Q = (0.2 \div 4.5) \text{ dm}^3 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$
PS1, PS2	Pressure sensor	$p = (0 \div 600) \text{ kPa}$
BV1-BV4	Ball valve	
MS 5070	Measuring device	

Figure 1. Schematic of the Experimental Setup

3.2 Measurement Methodology

For each tested particle size fraction of the sorbent, the pressure drop (Δp) was measured under defined volumetric flow rates (Q). During each experiment, the filtration column was filled with the same volume of sorbent, specifically $V = 31.4 \text{ cm}^3$, corresponding to a cylindrical segment with a diameter $D = 4 \text{ cm}$ and a height $h = 2.5 \text{ cm}$. The sorbent was not pre-compacted or pressed. It was gently loaded into the column to preserve the natural morphological characteristics of the

respective fraction. The sorbent bed was confined between two textile membranes, which prevented any displacement due to fluid flow.

All tests were carried out using distilled water as the working fluid.

Before each measurement series, the pressure sensors PS1 and PS2 were reset to zero to eliminate potential systematic errors in pressure drop determination. The flow rate Q was adjusted by changing the pump speed and was precisely recorded using the flowmeter FM. The pressure drop Δp was determined as the difference between the pressures recorded upstream and downstream of the filtration column. For each set flow rate, steady-state values were recorded, with the measurement range limited by the maximum capacities of the installed sensors.

Each experimental run was repeated three times under identical conditions to verify the reproducibility of the results. The outcome of each test was the dependence of the pressure drop Δp on the volumetric flow rate Q for a given particle size fraction and sorbent type.

4. Result evaluation

The measured pressure drop values were processed and graphically represented as a function of volumetric flow rate. For each sorbent material, a relationship $\Delta p = f(Q)$ was established, as illustrated in Figure 2. The results clearly demonstrate that the pressure drop increases with decreasing particle size.

Figure 2. Pressure drop (Δp) as a function of volumetric flow rate (Q) for different sorbents

For instance, the 40–80 μm fraction exhibited a pressure drop of approximately 80 kPa at a flow rate of 0.5 $\text{dm}^3\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, while the 160–200 μm fraction showed only about 12 kPa under the same conditions. This difference reflects the higher hydraulic resistance and lower permeability associated with finer fractions.

The ceramic sorbent cordierite with particle sizes below 40 μm exhibited significantly higher pressure drops than the cenospheres. A sharp increase in pressure drop was observed even at low flow rates — for instance, at 0.5 $\text{dm}^3\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, the pressure loss reached approximately 490 kPa.

This behaviour can be attributed to the fine particle structure of the material, its higher bulk density ($1.08 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$), and likely lower porosity.

From a practical standpoint, coarser cenosphere fractions (e.g., 160–200 μm) are more suitable for high-flow applications such as continuous columns, where low hydraulic resistance is essential. In contrast, Cordierite may be considered for low-flow dosing systems, where sorption efficiency takes precedence over permeability.

Conclusions

The experimental evaluation of pressure drop across various sorbent materials confirmed a strong dependence on both particle size and bulk density. Finer fractions, particularly the cordierite sorbent with particle sizes below 40 μm , exhibited significantly higher hydraulic resistance, limiting their applicability in high-flow systems.

In contrast, coarser cenospheres fractions (e.g., 160–200 μm) demonstrated lower pressure losses and higher permeability, making them suitable for continuous sorption processes. The choice of sorbent thus has a substantial impact on the energy demands of the process — selecting an appropriate particle size can help reduce pressure losses and consequently lower energy consumption for pumping during filtration. These findings underscore the importance of optimizing sorbent selection according to the hydraulic and operational requirements of the intended application.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in [Zenodo] at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14928686> [5].

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